

SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF CONFLICT SITUATIONS BETWEEN TEACHERS AND STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article deals with the causes of conflicts between a teacher and a teacher in the system of secondary schools, as well as measures for the prevention of pain, and provides the opinion of a number of scientific researchers on this issue.*

Keywords: *conflicts, upbringing, upbringing, conflictogenic, constructive, brainstorming, empathy, confrontation.*

There are various definitions of conflict, but they all emphasize the presence of contradiction, which takes the form of disagreement when it comes to human interaction. Conflicts can be hidden or explicit, but they are always based on a lack of agreement. Therefore, a conflict is defined as a lack of agreement between two or more parties - individuals or groups.

A conflict is a clash of opposing sides, opinions, forces, which is characterized by the activity of subjects aimed at resolving contradictions [1, p. 87].

Pedagogical conflict is a clash of oppositely directed goals, interests, positions of subjects of pedagogical interaction [2. p. 43].

A conflict situation does not always and does not necessarily lead to destruction, on the contrary, under certain conditions, even open conflicts can contribute to the preservation of the viability and stability of the social whole.

Conflict contains potential positive opportunities. The general idea of the positive effect of conflicts boils down to the following: “The productivity of confrontation stems from the fact that conflict leads to change, change leads to adaptation, adaptation leads to survival” [3, p. 35.]. If we stop perceiving conflict as a threat and start treating it as a signal that speaks about that we need to change something, we will take a more constructive position. The value of conflicts is that they prevent ossification of the system, open the way for innovation. Conflict is an incentive to change, it is a challenge that requires a creative reaction [10, p. 132].

Currently, in the theory and practice of pedagogy, a significant stock of facts and observations has been accumulated for an attempt to raise the question of the design of a theoretical direction - pedagogical conflictology, as an independent field of research in the science of education. The problem of pedagogical conflicts belongs to the field of scientific knowledge, which has its place in all sciences, both social and technical.

Pedagogical conflictology is a theoretical and applied direction, the main purpose of which is to study the nature and causes of pedagogical conflicts, to develop methods of their practical regulation and resolution [8, p. 45].

A conflict situation is a combination of human interests that creates the ground for a real confrontation between social actors [7, p. 79]. The main feature is the emergence of the subject of the conflict, but so far there is no open active struggle.

Considering conflict to be an effective means of educating a person, scientists point out that overcoming conflict situations is possible only on the basis of special psychological and

pedagogical knowledge and skills corresponding to them. Meanwhile, many teachers negatively assess any conflict as a phenomenon indicating failures in their educational work. Most teachers still have a cautious attitude towards the very word “conflict”, in their minds this concept is associated with deterioration of relationships, violation of discipline, a phenomenon harmful to the educational process. They tend to avoid conflicts by any means.

Pedagogical conflict itself is a normal social phenomenon, quite natural for such a dynamic society as a modern school [4, p. 32]. Modern conflictology orients the mass consciousness of people to understand the inevitability of conflicts in various spheres of human activity, including pedagogical. However, poor training of teachers and managers, inability to manage school conflicts in practice, to find optimal ways to prevent and overcome them, as a rule, negatively affect the organization of the educational process.

In pedagogical conflictology, theoretically, there is no distinction between such concepts as opponents, opposites, subjects, parties to the conflict. These concepts are synonymous in the view of many scientists.

A conflict situation is understood as an objective combination of various circumstances that precede the conflict and cause, as a rule, incompatible requirements for different persons. According to a number of researchers in pedagogy, a conflict situation precedes the conflict itself, its components are the subjects and object of the conflict with all their relationships and characteristics.

Thus, a conflict pedagogical situation can be taken as a set of objective and subjective conditions that arise in school society and create a certain psychological tension, due to which the rational control of the subjects of communication is weakened and their emotional perception of the existing contradictions is activated. In order for a conflict situation to escalate into a conflict, an incident is necessary. An incident is a reason for a conflict, a specific circumstance that is a “trigger mechanism” that generates the development of events. According to M. R. Bityanova, “an incident is a situation of interaction that allows its participants to realize the existence of an objective contradiction in interests and goals” [6, p. 8].

Pedagogical conflict is a complex phenomenon that occurs, as a rule, due to objective and subjective reasons. The objective reasons include the socio-economic situation of teaching in the whole country and specifically the specifics of the conditions of pedagogical activity in this area, district, educational institution. Subjective reasons are mainly related to the specifics of interpersonal relations in school society, due to the peculiarities of the psychological structure of the personality of each participant in the educational process, i.e. individual psychological, socio-psychological and scientific-ideological qualities of the individual. Thus, it can be said that pedagogical conflict, as a rule, arises on the basis of objective conditions with the appropriate inclusion of a subjective factor. However, there are many facts in practice that testify to the priority role of the subjective factor in provoking conflicts in school society.

Pedagogical conflicts have a number of features:

- the responsibility of the teacher for the pedagogically correct resolution of problematic situations: after all, the school is a model of society where students learn the norms of relations between people;
- participants in conflicts have different social status (teacher-student), which determines their behavior in the conflict;

- the difference in the life experience of the participants generates a different degree of responsibility for mistakes in conflict resolution;
- different understanding of events and their causes (the conflict “through the eyes of the teacher” and “through the eyes of the student” is seen differently), so it is not always easy for the teacher to understand the depth of the child's experiences, and for the student to cope with emotions, to subordinate them to reason;
- the presence of other students makes them participants from witnesses, and the conflict acquires an educational meaning for them as well; the teacher always has to remember this;
- the professional position of the teacher in the conflict obliges him to take the initiative in resolving it and put the interests of the student first.
- every mistake of the teacher in resolving the conflict generates new problems in which other students are involved. [5, p. 52].

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Conflict in pedagogical activity often manifests itself as a teacher's desire to assert his position and as a student's protest against unfair punishment, incorrect assessment of his activity, act.

Among the potentially conflictogenic pedagogical situations , the following can be distinguished:

- Conflicts of activity. They often arise in the classroom between a teacher and a student, a teacher and a group of students about the student's performance of educational tasks, academic performance. This can happen for various reasons: fatigue, difficulty in assimilating educational material, failure to complete homework, and often an unsuccessful remark by the teacher instead of concrete help in case of difficulties in work. Such conflicts often occur with students experiencing learning difficulties. Recently, there has been an increase in such conflicts due to the fact that teachers often make excessive demands on the assimilation of the subject, and marks are used as a means of punishing those who do not obey the teacher, violate discipline in the classroom.

- Conflicts of behavior arising from a student's violation of the rules of behavior at school, more often in the classroom, and outside of school, if the teacher made mistakes in analyzing the student's act, made an unreasonable conclusion, did not find out the motives. It should be borne in mind that the same act can be caused by completely different motives. The teacher has to correct the behavior of students through an assessment of their actions with insufficient information about the circumstances and the true reasons. The teacher is not always a witness to children's life, only guesses about the motives of the act, does not know the relationship between children well, so mistakes are quite possible when evaluating behavior, and this causes quite justified indignation of students. Teachers, assessing the actions of students, are not always responsible for the consequences of such assessments for the student and do not care enough about how such assessments will affect the subsequent relationship between the teacher and the student.

- Conflicts of relations arising in the sphere of emotional and personal relations between students and teachers, in the sphere of their communication in the process of pedagogical activity. Relationship conflicts acquire a personal meaning, generate a long-term dislike or hatred of the student towards the teacher, permanently disrupt interaction with the teacher and create an acute

need for protection against injustice and misunderstanding of adults. According to the content of the situations that arise between the teacher and the students, you can learn about the nature of the existing relationship between them, the positions of the teacher and the students.

Every situation, act and even conflict in the pedagogical work of a teacher with a competent analysis can be a valuable source of information about the personality of a student.

Interpersonal conflicts between a teacher and a pupil (teacher and student, parent and child) include pedagogical conflict. Consequently, pedagogical conflict is a special case of interpersonal conflict, and therefore it is characterized by the properties inherent in interpersonal conflicts, the corresponding patterns are fulfilled. The main distinguishing feature of the pedagogical conflict is the juxtaposition of socio-role positions. The nature of pedagogical conflicts is determined by the status of the participants in the conflict, the presence of legal, moral and professional responsibility of the administration of an educational institution and the teaching staff for the life, health of students and the results of educational activities; significant differences in age, life experience, civil rights, education of students and teachers, and other specific features. The conflict between a teacher and a student can be caused by many different reasons. In general, these reasons are similar for any interpersonal conflicts: the opposition of socio-role positions, goals, interests; psychological incompatibility; the presence of internal conflicts; lack of communicative culture, etc. Another reason for the conflict between the teacher and the student may be the lack of a communicative culture: intolerance to the other, inability to listen, tactlessness, rudeness to the other party, etc.

The child, starting from the first grade, is under severe pressure from teachers and the school as a whole. His working day begins with the fear of being late for school and fear of the sanctions that threaten for this, then he may be subjected to similar punishments for a forgotten notebook, textbook, compass, replacement shoes and other similar offenses. In addition to these “preliminary fears” that are not directly related to the educational process, during the lesson itself, the child is pursued by purely “educational fears”. Therefore, he is almost constantly in a state of sufficiently strong nervous excitement, which in itself creates a conflict situation. According to K. Levin, the frequency of conflicts in a group is determined by the “level of tension” in which a person or group exists. Conflicts are also caused by the presence of “external barriers” that do not allow a person to leave an unpleasant situation. The role of external barriers in the school is the obligation to attend classes, strict regulation of educational activities and behavior of the student. The degree of tension and the likelihood of conflict are also determined by the willingness of the parties to accept the partner's position. In school practice, it is the teacher, as a more experienced and trained communicator, who must perceive, understand and objectively evaluate the student's position.

It is known that only understanding the true causes of the conflict opens the way to their resolution [11, p. 176]. That is why the search and detection of the real causes of school conflicts is one of the most important tasks of pedagogical conflictology. Based on the considered views on the nature of conflicts, the following objective and subjective causes of pedagogical conflicts can be distinguished.

Objective causes of pedagogical conflicts:

- Insufficient degree of satisfaction of the basic needs of the child;
- The opposition of the functional role positions of the teacher and the student;
- Significant limitation of degrees of freedom;

- Differences in beliefs, values, life experience, belonging to different generations;
- Dependence of the student on the teacher;
- The need for teacher evaluation of students;
- Ignoring personal problems of students in formalized educational systems;
- The multiplicity of roles that a student is forced to play due to the different, sometimes opposite requirements imposed on him in an educational institution, by parents, comrades, or any other significant people;
- The difference between educational material and phenomena, objects of real life.

Subjective reasons include:

- Psychological incompatibility of teacher and student.
- The presence of certain character traits in the teacher or student that define the so-called “conflicted personality”;
- Lack of communicative culture of the teacher or student;
- The need for all students to study this subject and the lack of interest in it in a particular student 4
- The discrepancy between the intellectual and physical capabilities of this student and the requirements imposed on him;
- Insufficient competence of the teacher;
- Whether the teacher or student has serious personal problems, strong nervous tension, stress;
- Excessive workload of the teacher or student;
- Forced inactivity of the student;
- Lack of independence, creativity in the educational process;
- Discrepancy between the student's self-assessment and the assessment given to him by the teacher.

A conflict at school is a crisis development of a pedagogical situation characterized by a sharp aggravation of interpersonal relations and an increase in internal, mental tension of participants in the educational process [9, p. 45]. Its solution requires a significant strain of intellectual, emotional, spiritual forces of the educator and pupils. At the same time, there are situations when ignoring the conflict, the desire to avoid it by any means leads only to its prolongation, complication, transformation into more severe, difficult to resolve forms. In such situations, it is much more reasonable to allow the conflict to mature, to manifest itself in an open form so that, by controlling its course, it would be possible to come to a constructive solution to the problem and a positive result. However, quite often there are conflicts caused usually by subjective reasons, the development of which is absolutely hopeless, leads only to negative consequences. If appropriate actions are taken in a timely manner, then an undesirable development of the pedagogical situation can be avoided.

The conflict pedagogical situation is characterized by a sharp aggravation of the contradictions that have arisen in the interactions of the teacher and students, an increased degree of tension in interpersonal relations, represents a potential conflict. Conflicts are classified according to the relations of the status of participants: vertical (between teacher and students, parent and children) and horizontal (between students); by the degree of manifestation: open or hidden; by the degree of intensity: pronounced and erased; by reasons: generated by objective and

subjective reasons; by time of action - protracted and short-term, by value: constructive and destructive.

In modern conflictology, positive and negative functions of conflict are distinguished. Considering the conflict in the field of education and taking into account its specific features, the following positive functions of the conflict can be noted:

- informative function (obtaining new information about the participants of the conflict, diagnosis and clarification of the situation);
- integrative function (consolidation of the class, school, teaching staff in confrontation with an external enemy);
- innovative (stimulating the change and development of the personality of the teacher and student, their relationships, the organization of the educational process, schools, etc.);
- defusing tension between the conflicting parties
- gives a signal of trouble, allows you to more fully and accurately identify the overdue contradictions;
- provides a chance to develop the personality of the teacher, the student and the organization of the educational process at school.

Negative functions include:

- destructive function (damage to life, health, deterioration or collapse of relationships, inability to achieve the goals of education and personal development of the student, etc.);
- disintegration (destruction of the integrity of the individual, as well as the community, the system in which the conflict develops, dismissal of teachers, reduction of discipline of students, deterioration of the psychosocial climate in the collective of students and teachers);
- large emotional, material costs of participating in the conflict;
- a sharp decrease in the effectiveness of educational activities;
- occurrence of the "defeated" syndrome.

Thus, a pedagogical conflict can be considered as a form of manifestation of aggravated subject-subject contradictions arising as a result of professional and interpersonal interaction of participants in the educational process, which most often cause them a negative emotional background of communication, and offers a constructive translation of the clash of the parties to the conflict into an interested elimination of its causes. Thus, in this interpretation of pedagogical conflict as a kind of conflict in general, attention is primarily drawn to the scope of its course (the educational process), the peculiarity of the subjects (teachers and children), the emotional background of the course.

The conflict between a teacher and a student can be caused by many different reasons. In general, these reasons are similar for any interpersonal conflicts: the juxtaposition of socio-role positions, goals, interests; psychological incompatibility; the presence of internal conflicts; lack of communicative culture, etc. However, in practice, in the process of finding effective ways to resolve conflict situations at school, it makes sense to specify these reasons and consider them in the context of pedagogical activity. So, for example, a conflict between a teacher and a student may be caused by such a common cause as differences in intentions. Another reason for the conflict between the teacher and the student may be the lack of a communicative culture: intolerance to the other, inability to listen, tactlessness, rudeness to the other party, etc. Since the social status of a teacher in a traditional school is significantly higher than the social status of a student, tactlessness and rudeness on the part of a student is the exception rather than the rule and most

often represents a response to the corresponding words or actions of the teacher. Significantly more often it is “teachers” who make caustic remarks, insults to students, raise their voice, breaking into a shout, humiliate the personal dignity of schoolchildren, and are intolerant of the personal opinion of students. Such teachers, humiliating students, strive to rise above them, showing their strength and power. However, they cause mainly negative feelings of fear, irritation, hostility, resentment and revenge among students, interest in learning drops sharply, the desire to go to school disappears with the consequences that follow.

Understanding the true causes of the conflict opens the way to their resolution. That is why the search and the

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